

Extended Results

HUMETAV Model for Citizen Science Initiatives: Designing Socio-Ecological Projects for Awareness

This section follows the stages of Buchanan’s Design Process and Practice methodology during the co-creative construction of the *HUMETAV–CS* workshop. The process takes place after receiving seed funding from one of the institutions supporting educational innovation. This project involved researchers and doctoral students who were gradually integrated and considered as organisers of the initiative. Although the representatives of the participating institutions had already agreed on the initial idea for obtaining the funding, the formal planning and building of the workshop began with the official announcement of the funding. The researchers documented all research progress in online shared folders, including aspects such as project planning, databases, feedback, and evidence of implementation. We report retrospectively on the stages that led to the construction and testing of the citizen science workshop, with a view to the gradual validation of the *HUMETAV model*.

Stage 0 - Vision & strategy

The first stage focuses on discovering the ideas and circumstances to be taken into account for the development and piloting of the *HUMETAV–CS* workshop based on the *HUMETAV model*. It involves considering the vision of the organisations involved and the strategy of this co-creative endeavor. **Table 1** describes the characteristic activities of dialogue, strategic planning and strategic design planning, as well as the vision of the workshop development process.

Table 1. Description of the characteristic activities of Stage 0 (Vision & Strategy) of Buchanan’s Design Process and Practice methodology, applied to the design of the *HUMETAV–CS* workshop based on the *HUMETAV model*.

Characteristic Activities	Stage 0 – Vision & Strategy Description of the information gathered
Dialogue: To understand the institutional context for designing and piloting a citizen science workshop	In order to identify the guiding ideas and circumstances of the workshop to be developed (as suggested by the Design Process and Practice methodology), researchers from the two universities and the Museum of Environmental Sciences met. Through this dialogue, the complementary characteristics of the two universities were recognised, one being a public institution and the other a private non-profit institution, both serving students from the metropolitan area of Guadalajara, Mexico. In accordance with the Fund’s guidelines, institutions agreed that the workshop would focus on university students, but that teachers should also participate, regardless of the level at which they teach.
Strategic Planning: To identify the broader strategic flow that the project involves	In terms of content, it was considered from the outset to apply the HUMETAV model to the development of the new workshop, given its origins linked to the mission of the Environmental Science Museum. It was therefore proposed to review the previous HUMETAV-TD workshop, which took place in 2020, in order to inform the structure of

	the new initiative, which would focus on citizen science. Based on this experience, aspects such as the development schedule, the teamwork format, the web platform used, the recruitment methodology and the roles of the participants would be studied.
<p>Strategic design planning: To propose a project brief in line with the vision and strategy</p>	We completed this initial phase by preparing a design brief to guide the construction of the workshop. Following the allocation of funds, we agreed to launch the call for participation in ‘HUMETAV - Citizen Science, Training Young Scientists through the Design of Citizen Science Projects’. The objective was to promote the participation of communities from both educational institutions involved in the design of citizen science projects with a comprehensive socio-ecological impact where citizens contribute to the observation and documentation of facts and phenomena of the natural and social environment while developing the competence of complex thinking.

Stage 1 – Brief

In this stage, we sought to identify and select the initial problems, functions, and characteristics of the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop. Further research was undertaken to develop the call brief, including a review of the highlights of the previous *HUMETAV – TD* workshop. **Table 2** presents the key findings from this stage, describing the characteristic activities of discussion, scenario building, visualisation, and project planning.

Table 2. Description of characteristic activities of Phase 1 (Brief) of Buchannan’s Design Process and Practice methodology in relation to the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop.

Characteristic Activities	Stage 1 – Brief Description of the information gathered
<p>Discussion: To define the scope of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>The search of consensus among the researchers to decide on the scope of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop call for participation continued during this stage. A monthly meeting was set up for the research group members to participate in the construction of the brief and eventually the call itself. Benchmarking was carried out to understand the components commonly used in social and educational calls for participation. Key elements to be included were the institutions involved, the research leaders, the aim, the target audience, key dates, requirements for participation, guidelines, registration form, evaluation, and benefits. Once the sections had been decided, the theme and content of the project were discussed, for which it was essential to understand the origin and concepts involved of the <i>HUMETAV model</i> and the cornerstones of citizen science.</p>

Research

Objectives:

To study the *HUMETAV* – TD event and citizen science and render the *HUMETAV* model

To understand the *HUMETAV* model, we clarified that it aims to empower young people to become aware and act to integrate nature into the city through applied social research. The model also aims to introduce them to the emerging techno-creation infrastructures offered by the Museum of Environmental Sciences (e.g., makerspaces, virtual laboratories, extramural community development work, etc.) in order to carry out social innovation projects that could eventually be presented in the museum's exhibition halls and workshops. It was noted that *HUMETAV-TD* sought to promote networking with small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the region, especially those in the creative industries.

Learning from and building on the 2020 *HUMETAV-TD workshop* (Sanabria-Zepeda & Santana-Castellon, 2022), we aimed at introducing a similar format for the citizen science edition. The *HUMETAV-TD* workshop was delivered online to 40 participants over four weeks using Zoom and Miro technologies, led by the founders of the Transition Design Institute. In essence, Transition Design is defined as an emerging approach that aims to address complex problems and catalyse societal transitions towards a more sustainable future. It emphasises cross-sector collaboration, advocates multi-scale solutions (region, city, neighbourhood, household) and focuses on creating lifestyle-based visions of the future. It values everyday life as the central context for design, seeking emergent solutions and translating them into an ‘ecology of solutions’ to achieve long-term sustainable goals (Kossoff and Irwin, 2021).

Familiarisation with the *HUMETAV-TD* workshop process. In the workshop, teams of professors, students, and industry representatives, each paired with a mentor, analysed socio-ecological challenges in surrounding neighborhoods of the Museum of Environmental Sciences. Using a collaborative digital platform (Miro), they applied the TD approach to identify and analyse nine key issues in the Guadalajara metropolitan area. The workshop consisted of five weekly synchronous sessions that explored different elements of TD, such as mapping wicked problems and stakeholder relationships, mapping the historical evolution of the problem, designing a transition pathway and developing future visions, and finding futures and designing interventions. At the end of the workshop, the participating teams presented their intervention proposals. The detailed proceedings of the workshop were then materialised in a technical report available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5634581> (Sanabria-Z et al., 2021). A mirror activity was then carried out with university students to complete the diagnosis of a further four wicked problems, bringing the total to thirteen by the end of the programme.

In order to apply the *HUMETAV model* to the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop, we proceeded to summarise the knowledge gained in *HUMETAV-TD* workshop and familiarise the group with the basic

concepts of citizen science. Many aspects of the *HUMETAV-TD* workshop experience was noteworthy: the flexible online working dynamic allowed for multidisciplinary collaboration despite the competing schedules of participants. The methodological structure of the Transition and the open access to each other's processes and presentations encouraged systemic thinking by all members. In the teams, despite the presence of an assigned mentor, leadership was distributed, with roles changing naturally based on the weekly deliverables, rather than one individual standing out.

In terms of settings and materials during the workshop, it was found that participants appreciated the user-friendly digital layout on collaborative interactive boards. The instructional design was also found to be appropriate to the objectives, with workshop leaders presenting and recording the weekly sessions, sharing digital resources by topic, and providing feedback during the week on the team boards with the support of mentors.

Despite the successes of the programme, some areas for improvement were identified. The depth of work required by the weekly activities could only be addressed to a limited extent because participants were not fully engaged in the workshop. Furthermore, while it would have been ideal to engage with stakeholders to fully diagnose the issues raised, this could only be done on an ad hoc basis by telephone. Also, the final deliverables had a limited and varied structure, so there is room for improvement to create a consistent format for a research document with specific sections, with the possibility of a future funding application to support this proposal.

We sought to use resources within and outside the research group to support the workshop's methodological framework, toolkits and guidance. In particular, the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) website was selected as a source of news, materials, events and potential contacts for citizen science experts. It was also decided to adopt Robinson et al.'s (2018) Ten Principles of Citizen Science as a general guideline, which is recognised as a globally accepted document in the field. Given its relevance to the project, collaboration with representatives of the European Academy of Citizen Science project was proposed for expert support in the evaluation of projects to improve citizen science education and training.

More specifically, it was decided to use the Threshold for Citizen Science Projects (TCSP) framework (Sanabria-Z et al., 2022) as a central framework for project design and impact assessment, as it is at the core of the methodology promoted by members of the research group of this project. This framework defines three levels of impact (bounded, threshold and full-cycle citizen science). It is guided by eight assessment components: context awareness, citizen engagement, infrastructure

	leverage, technological innovation, educational innovation, outreach and scale, network building, and complex thinking.
<p>Scenario building: To identify actors, spaces, technologies, and interactions for the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>It was decided that the opening event would be held at the Museum of Environmental Sciences of the University of Guadalajara, to provide participants with a context of the museum's mission and infrastructure. However, it was decided that the final presentation and closing ceremony would take place at the Congress Palace of the Tecnologico de Monterrey, to create a more academic atmosphere. We also decided to design a web platform through a software development company.</p>
<p>Visualisation: To draft the configuration of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>We decided to hold a weekly synchronous meeting of the research teams and to send reminders to the participating researchers by email and messenger to mark the implementation of the activities. The first step in designing the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop configuration was to make the project brief tangible, facilitated by the organisers' creation of the project timeline and the outline of the call for participation. The call was to be published jointly by local institutions: the Institute for the Future of Education (IFE) of the Tecnologico de Monterrey, the Museum of Environmental Sciences and the Department of Sustainability and Territorial Sciences of the University Centre of Tlajomulco, University of Guadalajara. It was aimed at undergraduate students from both institutions, with the aim of promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and a wide range of viewpoints.</p> <p>The use of the eight components of the TCSP framework was linked not only to the development of content modules for participants, but also as selection criteria to prioritise proposals with clear objectives and practical implementation plans. Guidelines for team collaboration were suggested, including the use of web-based tools such as messengers.</p> <p>In addition, the role of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop platform was identified as a cross-cutting priority for the success of the project, as it would be the main interaction of the participants with the learning materials and the delivery of tasks to the participants.</p>
<p>Project Planning: To prepare a timetable and description of activities</p>	<p>Project planning included monthly meetings, plus three working teams with specific tasks: research products and call and workshop logistics; data collection tools and ethical requirements; citizen science content, mentoring, and <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop platform requirements. In the larger all-researcher sessions, the teams presented progress on their thematic tasks, while in the sub-sessions, they progressed the related tasks. The timeline was developed according to the deadlines and budget set by the Novus Fund supporting the project, i.e., the project had to be implemented within a maximum period of 6 months. At this stage, the necessary contacts for implementation were also reviewed, including those related to physical space, suppliers, and human resources.</p>

Stage 2 – Conception

In this second stage of the methodology, aimed at invention and judgement, we present the first proposal of the *HUMETAV* model applied to the *HUMETAV - Citizen Science* workshop. The project researchers co-created its structure incrementally and iteratively, through a development based on the design process approach and complementary methodologies. Its feasibility was assessed at each iteration. The formulation of the workshop, which ultimately served to test the model, required proposing the type of technological platform to be developed, the methodologies to be integrated, and the instructional design to guide the participants to achieve the expected outcomes of the workshop. Planning the configuration of the experience for the participants integrated the call for participation, the didactic sequence, the mentoring role, the presentation of the results, and the evaluation process. Table 3 describes the research, brainstorming, and early and frequent visualisation activities according to their objectives.

Table 3. Description of characteristic activities of stage 2 (Conception) of Buchannan’s Design Process and Practice methodology in relation to the co-creation of the *HUMETAV–CS* workshop.

Characteristic Activities	Stage 2 – Conception Description of the information gathered
<p>Research: To decide the structure of the platform and the instructional design of the workshop</p>	<p>The <i>HUMETAV–CS</i> workshop platform will serve as a landing page for the dissemination of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop, while being the main interactive space for the participants, hosting the activities and content managed by the organisers and trainers. It was also envisaged that it would host the input and output questionnaires on the participants' perception of complex thinking and their perception of civic participation. It will store the activities of the participating teams and serve as a point of interaction between the different roles involved, both from a management and a participant point of view.</p> <p>A sequence of 14 didactic modules will guide the <i>HUMETAV–CS</i> workshop work - TD boards at the start and end, and TCSP framework components in the middle. Their instructional design was assigned to the three participating research teams.</p>
<p>Brainstorming :To ideate the call launch process, platform interface, and participant deliverables.</p>	<p>The format of the call for participation was established as an online PDF document with hyperlinks to registration forms. The workshop learning modules combined TD with the eight components of the TCSP framework. Lessons learned from the previous workshop and other applications of the framework were taken into account. Mentoring activities were decided based on the previous experience of the <i>HUMETAV–TD</i> workshop. These involved PhD students from both universities.</p> <p>The evaluation process for the participating teams would include feedback and final assessment elements. Participating teams would produce three types</p>

	of deliverables: 1) a poster for the conference, with feedback from representatives of the European Academy of Citizen Science; 2) an oral presentation during the closing event; and 3) a research protocol, the central deliverable responding to the call for participants.
<p>Early and frequent visualisation:</p> <p>To monitor the progress of the call and the platform</p>	During iterative meetings, including event dates, logistics and commitments, we developed the final details of the call for participants, which we decided to launch via digital media (e.g. social media). We also started working with the service provider on the design of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop platform, which would be progressive and modular, and would run in parallel with the duration of the workshop. We proposed how to use the TCSP framework in the platform and combine it with an external platform for the Transition Design activities. We intended that participants in the call would use the first version of the platform as co-creators and identify improvements that needed to be made to the navigation.

Stage 3 – Realisation

This stage focused on the piloting of the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop. Here we explain how the *HUMETAV* model was applied and tested in the design of the citizen science workshop, based on the three months of experience with participants recruited through the call. Topics covered include the launch of the call, the opening the event, the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop platform, teamwork, outcomes, evaluation and the closing of the event. Table 4 describes characteristic activities, including research, scenario building and refinement, visualisation, and construction.

Table 4. Description of characteristic activities of Stage 3 (Realisation) of the Buchannan Design Process and Practice methodology related to the testing of the *HUMETAV* model through the piloting of the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop.

Characteristic Activities	Stage 3 – Realisation Description of the information gathered
<p>Research:</p> <p>To validate the ethical, technical, and financial aspects of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>We submitted an institutional application for exemption to the Institutional Ethics Committee with a research protocol that focused on secure data management and informed consent of participants. The committee reviewed the level of risk according to the nature of the research, monitoring the handling of personal data of participants, especially students, and the impact of the use of technology or other equipment and tools. We also initiated the process of a research collaboration agreement between the two organising institutions. The agreement covered issues of co-publication, joint decisions on intellectual property and other aspects of the research, making it clear that the issue of funding was controlled by the applicant organisation. Pending ethics committee approval, we proceeded to launch the call for participants, outlining the requirements, guidelines and evaluation criteria.</p>

We announced the call for participants on institutional websites and social networks, open to up to 20 teams of educators from both universities in the Guadalajara Metropolitan Area, and ran from 1 July to 27 August 2023. The *HUMETAV-CS* workshop, from August to December 2023, aimed to design citizen science projects while developing complex thinking skills. It included virtual asynchronous and synchronous work of the teams on the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop platform and communication through email and social networks. The call outlined the requirements, guidelines, and evaluation criteria, as well as relevant deadlines, emphasising the voluntary nature of participation and the benefits of collaboration between students and teachers. Requirements included designing proposals that contribute to scientific knowledge and address socio-ecological issues with the potential for meaningful community impact. Guidelines included timely submission, clear objectives aligned with citizen science themes, feasibility of data collection, integration of SDGs, and coherent argumentation. Six briefing sessions were planned to explain the specifics of the call to potential participants. Also, three training sessions were scheduled to register participants online, monitor the teams' progress, and present the final deliverables.

The technical requirements included that the evaluation of the projects would respond to rubrics that were aligned with criteria created from the TCSP framework and the 10 principles of citizen science. The evaluation of the projects co-created in the teams was based on their adherence to the established guidelines, their potential impact in addressing socio-ecological challenges and their appropriateness to the objectives of the initiative. Two rubrics were included in the evaluation criteria developed by the research group and applied to the project evaluation process. A first rubric was dedicated to the evaluation of each project according to the threshold level of citizen science applied in the project (Sanabria-Z et al., 2022). This rubric included evaluation according to the following criteria: consideration of context, involvement of citizens, approach to infrastructure, implementation of technological and pedagogical innovations, outreach and scale, network building and development of complex thinking. A second rubric addressed ten principles of citizen science (ECSA, 2023) and included: citizens contribute to knowledge; citizen science generates scientific outcomes; scientists and citizens benefit from each other; citizens can be involved at all stages; continuous communication is essential for citizens; citizen science has research boundaries to manage; data and results should be openly accessible; citizen contributions must be publicly recognised; evaluation by output, quality and impact; leaders address legal, ethical responsibilities.

Another technical aspect we considered was to ensure access to the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop platform and activities for both participants and project managers, as well as the possibility of receiving continuous feedback from users to be resolved by the commissioning company or in case of content by the researchers. During weekly meetings with the contractor, we monitor the ongoing performance and implementation of the feedback.

	<p>The project managers, supported by specialists from the institution assigned to assist with the management of the fund, oversaw the application and payment for the development of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop platform, promotional materials and cafeteria services during the opening and closing events. These were activities that had been declared in the application to the Fund and had to be monitored to the letter so that they could be reported at the end of the project.</p>
<p>Scenario building and refinement: To adjust team configuration and confirm venues</p>	<p>We distributed the tasks among the researchers, who would be supervising the development of the workshop over the 3 months. The tasks included the creation of research tools, supervision of the development of the platform, creation of content for the modules, communication with the teams, review of progress in the fulfilment of institutional aspects of the project.</p> <p>For the opening ceremony, we reserved a continuous auditorium at the Museum of Environmental Sciences. At the kick-off, promotional items would be handed out during registration, and the context of the project would be explained. During the event, teams would be organised to take a guided tour of the museum, which was still in the final stages of construction.</p> <p>For the closing ceremony, we arranged a hall in the Congress Centre of the Tecnológico de Monterrey for the final presentations and invited two speakers in the field of citizen science. We planned for the teams to present their results to the audience and for there to be a poster exhibition of the projects during the event. We agreed that at the end of the event we would award prizes to the first three places and give special mentions to the participating teams.</p>
<p>Visualisation: To test the final version of the platform interface</p>	<p>We validated the functioning of the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop platform's administrative functions, as well as the format of the modules that participants would navigate through and the resulting data analysis section. We approved the first modules with content, monitoring both functionality and instructional design. The activities related to the TCSP framework were carried out on the platform, while the activities related to TD were carried out on the Miro collaborative platform. Login tests were conducted for platform managers, teachers and participants. The participants, as users of the initial version of the platform, acted as co-creators and identified potential improvements in the navigation of the platform.</p>
<p>Construction: To implement and evaluate the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>The results of the workshop were evaluated in this section. Building the project involved refining the working platform, planning the spaces and activities for the opening and closing events, and meeting the requirements of the call for proposals, which were in line with the funding received for the project.</p> <p>We completed the recruitment of the participating teams and organised the assignment of a mentor to each team. The briefing sessions were poorly attended as they coincided with the summer holidays. Of the eleven teams that responded to the call, eight completed the workshop. The teams' performance was contrasted. It was necessary to restructure from 11 to 8 teams to reach the target. The mentors maintained close contact with their assigned teams.</p>

However, the impact of their role could not be observed due to changes in the configuration of the team members, which were made along the way.

The didactic sequence was effectively assimilated into the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop platform and helped the teams to complete the project proposals on time. The effective development of the proposals integrated the conceptual frameworks defined to define the citizen science projects.

The teams received feedback from the European Citizen Science Academy before the final presentations and also had the opportunity to hear from two citizen science experts who spoke at the closing event, a professor on behalf of Tecnológico de Monterrey and online from the leader of the European Citizen Science Academy. We, the main researchers from both institutions and the Museum of Environmental Sciences, assessed the proposals' clarity and coherence of the proposals, the feasibility of their implementation, and their potential to contribute to scientific knowledge. Proposals were also assessed for their innovation, interdisciplinary approach, and inclusion of the SDGs as part of their impact strategy.

The first three places were awarded to:

- 1st place, Irregular settlements in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga.
- 2nd place, Air quality monitoring and prevention of respiratory problems.
- 3rd place, Citizen Science Strategy for the Management of Single-Use Plastics.

The following projects received special commendations:

- Highest Outreach, for the project Vulnerability and Water Security in the Context of Climate Change, in Tlajomulco de Zúñiga.
- Participation, for the project Transport without panic - ZMG.
- Innovation, for the project Fast Fashion: Environmental and Health Impacts.
- Excellence in Education, for the project Design and elaboration of a functional food based on the modification of the microbiota for children between 1 and 4 years old with high marginalisation, users of the Xamixtli AC Community Centre.
- Excellence in Networking, for the project Phytoremediation and implementation of green roofs for the remediation of the Arroyo Seco.

The didactic sequence was effectively assimilated as the teams completed the project proposals as scheduled. The effective development of the proposals integrated the conceptual frameworks that were defined to define the citizen science projects.

During the course of the workshop, we obtained the exemption letter from the Ethics Committee and completed the signing of the Inter-institutional Agreement, both of which took longer than expected. On the other hand,

	Commitments relating to expenditure supported by the Fund were met and declared on time.
--	--

In summary, the didactic sequence of the implementation of the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop included several phases. In the first phase, following the open call to invite those interested in participating (students and teachers from the participating institutions), we held a first introductory session to the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop, in which the objectives and process were explained, as well as the ten principles of citizen science. Then, in a second phase, we held weekly videoconferences to exchange information on the activities that would enable them to identify and detect socio-environmental problems. For the process of identifying and defining the problems, we used the TD approach. After defining the problems, during the weekly sessions we shared the eight components of the TCSP framework. Each component was accompanied by short activities to outline the project prototypes. The teams then built the prototypes, which were finally presented in a face-to-face format at a final event. Both the content and the didactic activities were displayed on the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop platform.

Stage 4 - Delivery

In this last stage, the methodology led to the overall presentation, including the final product's prototype, documentation, and specifications. It was assimilated as the result of applying the *HUMETAV* model in the design and experience of the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop. Table 5 shows the characteristic elements of the model applied to the citizen science workshop (a written presentation), the evidence of the applied model (demonstration of the prototype), and the diagram of the model applied to citizen science (visual representation).

Table 5. Description of characteristic activities of stage 4 (Delivery) of Buchanan's Design Process and Practice methodology related to the *HUMETAV-CS* workshop results and the visualization of the *HUMETAV* model applied.

Characteristic Activities	Stage 4 – Delivery Description of the extracted information
<p>Written presentation: To describe the <i>HUMETAV</i> model as applied in the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop.</p>	<p>The <i>HUMETAV</i> model is framed within a five-helix innovation environment and five sustainability components, focusing on the theme and context of the institutional mission and purpose of the Museum of Environmental Sciences. The model addresses wicked problems using the TD approach and contextualises the solution ideation process with thematic frameworks, leading to the development of techno-creative and social entrepreneurship projects that respond to the particular context and needs.</p> <p>Its application in the design and piloting of the workshop involved adding existing citizen science principles to define the scope and the TCSP framework as a requirement for problem processing. That is, participants were introduced to the ten principles of citizen science as a set of guidelines that a citizen</p>

	<p>science project should consider in order to promote citizen involvement in the identified problem and ultimately the democratisation of science.</p> <p>The eight components that configure the TCSP framework were considered as guiding criteria for the proposal and design of citizen science projects by the workshop participants. Each of the components was presented through a didactic sequence that included a module for each component. In them, it was presented what each component consisted of and what its scope and implications could be.</p> <p>The <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop platform dedicated to the project acted as a catalyst and fundamental space for the personalisation of content and learning. The process of creating a supportive platform also enabled the involvement of researchers and allowed participants to link their contribution to an ongoing research project.</p>
<p>Prototype demonstration n To evidence the application of the <i>HUMETAV</i> model to the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>Overall, we managed to reflect the structural learning from the HUMETAV-TD workshop in the design and implementation of the HUMETAV-CS workshop. In particular, we noticed a smooth connection and assimilation between the TD approach and the TCSP framework during the practical part of the workshop.</p> <p>We observed that the achievements of the teams showed that the modelled pathway had a greater scope of specificity of deliverables compared to the previous workshop. Similar to HUMETAV-TD, the inter-university integration was a positive factor, which made the joint organisation of the event natural.</p> <p>The implementation of the original HUMETAV-CS workshop platform was a strong point for the pedagogical involvement of teams and researchers.</p>
<p>Visual representation n To diagram the <i>HUMETAV</i> model as applied to the <i>HUMETAV-CS</i> workshop</p>	<p>In reviewing the application of the HUMETAV model in the experience of the HUMETAV-CS workshop, we were able to establish that the key points that were introduced corresponded satisfactorily to the flow promoted by the model.</p> <p>Following the bottom-up flow of the model, it can be seen that the aspect of identifying wicked problems in relation to context and needs was successful in helping to identify the pressing issues in the participants' locations. Entering the Transition Design approach processes had the expected effect of delimiting the problems, their stakeholders, imagining the ideal future and proposing how to move towards it, taking into account the fivefold innovation helix.</p> <p>The thematic framing with the TCSP framework and the 10 Principles of Citizen Science was crucial to guide the proposals in the expected direction of the workshop. This was supported by the dedicated web platform created for the workshop, where they were able to prototype their proposed solutions.</p>

	<p>In the final stage, the creation of evaluation criteria derived from the thematic frameworks allowed for comprehensive results in the technocreative research protocols that could be turned into ventures. All this was framed and accompanied by the vision of the two institutions involved and in the spirit of the mission of the Museum of Environmental Sciences.</p>
--	---